

Physico-chemical and Bacteriological Analysis of Water from The Chandan River (South Bihar) India

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- Abstract** Life on Earth is unimaginable without water. Water is one of life's most precious resources. Clean water is like nectar for humans. However, anthropogenic waste, industrial waste, pesticides and insecticides used in agriculture, etc., are affecting water quality. Access to clean water is becoming increasingly difficult for every citizen. This research paper studies the physical, chemical, and biological parameters like temperature, pH, TDS, turbidity, DO, BOD, COD, alkalinity, turbidity, EC, Cl^- , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and hardness of the water samples at different sites of Chandan River in South Bihar.
- Keywords** Chandan river, Water analysis, Catchment area, Pollutants, Bihar.
- Introduction** Water is the second most life-giving natural substance on Earth, after air. The growth of every living organism and plant is possible only through water. Therefore, the deteriorating water situation poses a threat to both humanity and the ecosystem. Increasing industrialization, population explosion, and excessive use of fertilizers in agriculture have severely impacted water quality. Therefore, maintaining water cleanliness is an urgent need today¹⁰.
- three quarters of the Earth's surface is covered with water, but less than one percent of it is usable, so water must be used very carefully so that future generations can still have the water they need. Physical, chemical, and biological tests are used to determine water quality and its suitability for use without negative health effects¹¹.
- Pure water is vital for the survival of all living species. Therefore, its purification and quality monitoring are essential to minimize its adverse effects on health and the environment⁷.
- Objective of study** This research paper studies the physical, chemical, and biological parameters like temperature, pH, TDS, turbidity, DO, BOD, COD, alkalinity, turbidity, EC, Cl^- , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and hardness of the water samples at different sites of Chandan River in South Bihar.
- Review of Literature** The population of most countries on the African and Asian continents is rapidly increasing, which naturally increases the demand for fuel, housing, food, medicine, and new construction projects. As a result, rivers and groundwater are not only being rapidly exploited, but harmful substances are also being released into them. This has endangered the very existence of fauna and flora. Workers, farmers, washermen, fishermen, etc. living along the river banks depend on this water for their livelihoods⁸. The Chandan River is an important river in southern Bihar, flowing through the districts of Banka, Bhagalpur, and Munger and eventually merging with the Ganges. Historically, the river was known as the Champa River, marking the boundary between Magadha and Anga, two of the sixteen Mahajanapadas^{4,5}.
- Methodology** A total of 10 sites were identified for water sampling in the Chandan River catchment area. Water samples were collected at 10-day intervals from July 01, 2025, to August 10, 2025. Clean two-litre polyethylene bottles were used to collect water samples, and separate dark bottles were collected for BOD analysis. Physical and chemical parameters of the water were determined using standard methods^{1,2,6,8,13}. The 10 water sampling

sites are shown in Table 1.

Sl. No.	Site No.	Sampling sites
1	CH-1	Lachmipur (Banka District)
2	CH-2	Rupsa Village (Rajoun Block, Banka District)
3	CH-3	Chandan Village (Chanan Block, Banka District)
4	CH-4	Khajuria Village (Sonhaura Block, Banka District)
5	CH-5	Shankarpur Village (Colgong Block, Banka District)
6	CH-6	Indrabaran (Banka District)
7	CH-7	Goradih (Banka District)
8	CH-8	Pratapnagar Village (Naugachhia Block, Bhagalpur District)
9	CH-9	Kharik Village (Bhagalpur District)
10	CH-10	Dhuraiya (Bhagalpur District)

Study Area

The Chandan River originates at an altitude of 274 metres in the Deoghar Hills of Jharkhand state and travels approximately 110 kilometres through three districts of Bihar (Banka, Bhagalpur, Munger) before joining the Ganges River via the Jamunia Nala. Some of its major tributaries are the Orhani, Kudar, and Chatri. Its total catchment area is 4,093 square kilometres. The latitude and longitude at the Chandan River's source are $25^{\circ}23'$ and $86^{\circ}95'$, respectively, and the latitude and longitude at its destination are $25^{\circ}22'$ and $87^{\circ}04'$, respectively. Total ten sampling sites of this river have been selected for the present study^{3,4,5,14}.

Result and Discussion

The present study was conducted by collecting water samples at 10-day intervals from 10 sampling sites of the Chandan River, which flows through Banka, Munger and Bhagalpur districts. The study was conducted from July 1, 2025, to August 10, 2025. This timeframe was chosen due to the seasonal nature of the river, which flows primarily during the monsoon season. To assess the river's water quality and pollution levels, samples collected from the sampling sites were tested for physicochemical and bacteriological parameters^{1,9,12}. The parameters of the river water samples are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Average, Results of parameters of various samplings sites:

Site	Temp.	Hardness	Turbidity	Alkalinity	TDS	pH	EC	DO	BOD	Cl ⁻	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺
CH-1	32.8	620	85	240	370	7.2	310	6.2	14.1	110	39	158
CH-2	33.2	600	80	235	380	7.2	315	6.3	16.4	112	35	152
CH-3	32.6	610	72	225	375	7.4	330	6.3	15.8	113	37	149
CH-4	32.7	580	86	240	380	7.3	335	6.4	17.9	118	38	142
CH-5	33.0	550	92	245	390	7.5	350	6.6	18.2	117	34	137
CH-6	32.6	580	95	245	390	7.4	350	6.9	18.6	121	33	135
CH-7	33.4	590	90	250	380	7.6	370	6.8	20.1	123	30	131
CH-8	32.8	610	85	260	395	7.5	355	6.9	20.9	128	28	129
CH-9	33.6	600	88	265	400	7.8	370	7.3	22.6	125	26	123
CH-10	33.2	630	94	270	410	7.9	390	7.3	24.3	132	25	121

Table 3: Comparison of water samples of the studied area with WHO and BIS drinking standards^{9,10,12}.

Parameters	WHO (Standards)		Indian (Standards)		Observed Average value
	P	E	P	E	
pH	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.0-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.2-7.9
Ca ²⁺	75	200	75	200	121-158
Mg ²⁺	30	100	50	150	25-39
Cl	200	600	250	1000	110-132
Turbidity	-	10 NTU	-	10 NTU	72-95
Alkalinity	-	-	200	600	225-270
T. Hardness	300	600	100	500	580-630

All parameters are given in mg/L except EC (µmhos /cm) and turbidity (NTU), P = Permissible limit, E = Excessive limit

The comparison of various parameters at different sites is shown in the bar diagram given below.

Conclusion

The present study describes the detailed physicochemical characteristics and water quality of the Chandan River (South Bihar). Significant seasonal fluctuations in various physicochemical parameters were observed during the two monsoon months of July and August. Turbidity levels in the river were found to be higher during the rainy season. Although TDS and alkalinity values in the Chandan River water were acceptable, it is necessary to treat the river water before using it for drinking. River water can be used directly for agriculture, but it can only be used for livestock or specific types of agriculture after treatment. Public awareness is also needed to maintain the Chandan River water at the highest quality and purity. Continuous monitoring of pollution levels and preventing direct discharge of agricultural waste into the river are essential to improve water quality.

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